

HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT - AXIOLOGICAL FIELD OF INCREASING MANAGEMENT EFFICIENCY

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Abstract

Purpose – is to define the concept of human resources management and quality management, to identify methods to create managerial efficiency

Methodology/approach - The methodological plan of the paper consists in consulting the specialized literature and, based on the bibliographic study.

Findings – Following the bibliographic study, in each direction of research, it was observed that the literature has some limitations in the direction of empirical studies on measuring labor productivity in public administration, the object of research being treated only theoretically.

Research limitations/implications – Limitations for research consist in creating a research methodology, based on bibliographic studies, care will be based on subsequent qualitative and quantitative analysis.

Practical implications – *In the future, the application of the methodology will serve to create a management model that will successfully contribute to the administrative reform process. The pragmatic goal is to determine the methods of increasing labor productivity in public administration.*

Originality/value – The novelty consists in the fact that it can provide the managers of some preschool educational institutions, but also of some political decision-makers, the necessary information and knowledge regarding the human resources practices and their applicability in the management of the activities at the workplace.

Key words: *management, quality, education*

Introduction

Due to the fact that the staff resource, its profile and quality represent a true *primum movens* of the activity, the inherent competitive framework determines a real "battle" for attracting true professionals in the field of education, through managerial methods that include offering an activity environment that stimulates and ensures pro-performance means and behaviors, up to concrete motivational attitudes, usually quantified financially. Pursuing the achievement of performance criteria, the quality growth policy must stimulate not only the fulfillment of the benchmarks in the individual specifications, but it also must focus on the creative, innovative, individual and collective effort, reflected on the employee-institution-manager relationship or motivation and performance-management. Education and its management, viewed from the perspective of increasing the quality of teaching, were and remain open to interdisciplinary study, imposed not only by the emergence, but also by their evolution and subsequent implications at the social level. There are aspects that dynamically pigmented the surprising fresco of the historical evolution of research related to personnel management at different levels, being the object and concomitant subject of research for: E. B Filippo (1976) D. Farnham (2000 and 1986), J Storey (1995), PMWright & GC McMahan (1992), T. Keenoy (1990), M. Armstrong (1987).

Conceptualization of a syntagm: M.R.U

In order for all organizational development efforts to increase managerial efficiency through procedures that increase the staff quality and its success, managers must consider the fact that human resources are the most valuable asset of an institution, regardless of type or field of activity, that is why, through a semiotic mediation, the phrase human capital was established, together with the financial capital. Its management has often been able to ensure the difference between success and failure, between performance and mediocrity, from overcoming the stage in which the workforce had only an accounting relevance, expressing employment, pay and possible dismissal.

Emphasizing the importance of the structure and professional level of human resources, William H. Newman, since 1964, in *Process of Management: Strategy, Action, Results*, defined management as "an important social technique, that directing, leading and controlling efforts a group of individuals, in order to achieve a certain common goal. " In 1969, in the November-December issue of the famous American publication *Harvard Business Review*, Alec MacKenssie defined the concept of management in a three-dimensional internal architecture: ideas, things and people. In France, in 1966, Octave Glinier's work entitled *The Secret of Competitive Structures* appeared, in which the French researcher considers that management designates, both, leadership and organization, but at the same time requires a conscious methodical and scientific effort to study and achieve the conditions. optimal activity of the organization's staff.

Peter Drucker (1985) states in the same direction that the main task of the manager is to mobilize the energies of the economic unit to fulfill known and defined tasks.

Unlike the traditional approach, on this category of resources, the postmodern interpretation focuses on highlighting the implications that human resources can manifest in achieving the managerial target. The research of the complex issue of personnel resources, through the work signed by Rosalind H. Searle & Denise Skinner (2011) is positioned in a psychoanalytic perspective which emphasizes the phenomenology of mutual trust as a link between the staff of an organization.

The art of internal resource management

Internal resources are those characteristics of an organization that can be used to achieve a certain managerial strategy. These include not only tangible features such as buildings, staff and finances, but also intangible features such as reputation as an expression of the team's professionalism. The analysis should cover not only the presence of these resources, but also how they are used or exploited. Thus, a school could have untapped potential, for example, in its buildings or the quality of its staff or it may have additional potential in its relations with potential financiers. Therefore, a realistic assessment of all opportunities must be made, as this will be part of any assessment of possible future strategies to increase the quality of work generated by increasing the level of professionalism of human resources. It is essential not only that all possibilities be assessed, but also to eliminate overly optimistic assumptions, as this would jeopardize the viability of any strategy. The strengths and weaknesses of the school's current operations should result from the audit of resources.

As it is natural, organizational performance must be evaluated. Such an assessment must use clear comparative data. How well does the organization work compared to similar institutions and especially local competing institutions? For schools, kindergartens, this means an analysis of test and exam results and other results at different levels of schooling. Surveys on the opinions of staff, parents and alumni can thus provide data on the strengths and weaknesses they perceive about the institution. Such information is essential for the formation of the educational strategy but also in tracing the design of the professional portrait of teachers.

How the personnel policy influences the establishment of the qualitative parameters of the activity

If according to Peter F. Drucker's (1993) definition, built around the concept of "human resources", "management means organizing resources to achieve satisfactory performance and economic activity based on material and human resources", newer studies show that the issue of the quality of education has become significant for the social environment because all aspects and fundamental activities of

civilization begin and are dependent on the level of education and as an expression of it, the quality of human resources involved in this activity. Among the important directions which depend on the personnel resource, orient the managerial activity here some of them can be mentioned:

- combining leadership and personal responsibility;
- promoting staff on the basis of competence and professionalism, efficiency and effectiveness.

These are not negligible aspects, especially when the level of staff training is obviously reflected in a deficient managerial act. In this regard, in the field of educational management, the following principles are activated to increase quality: 1- the principle of efficiency involves the use of managerial methods and techniques to ensure the achievement of the institution's objectives with maximum efficiency; 2- the principle of motivation can be achieved by establishing and using moral and material stimuli by senior managers to interest the organizational behavior of all to achieve the proposed objectives; 3- the principle of participatory management, refers to the employment of employees in solving processes and management relations, regardless of their complexity (it was found that this involvement increases the degree of loyalty, motivation, participation in system functionality and increases efficiency); 4 - the principle of correlation between possibilities and requirements expresses the need to adapt the management system to the demands of external factors by increasing quality.

Therefore, we can consider that the director of educational institutions and by extension, any person engaged in a reform process, must have a behavior similar to that described by Harvard Professor Chris Argyris (1985) who declares as effective behavior of the manager , in the process of improving the quality of staff, everything that "beings use to deal with these problems."

The aspects presented by the scheme elaborated by Robbins and Coulter are deepened in specialized studies (see: James C. Craig & Robert M. Grant, Strategic Management, Kogan Page, 1993; Julia Balogun & Veronica Hope-Hailey, Exploring Strategic Change, Prentice-Hall Europe, 1999; Adrian Haberberg & Alison Rieple, The Strategic Management of Organizations, Prentice-Hall, 2001; Andrew Campbell & Kathleen Sommers Luchs (eds.), Core Competency-Based Strategy, International Thomson, 1997; Paul Joyce & Adrian Woods, Essential Strategic Management - from modernism to pragmatism, Heinemann, 1996; Robert Paton & James McCalman, Change Management - A guide to effective implementation, 2nd Edition, Sage, 2000; Gary Hamel & CK Prahalad, Competing for the Future, Harvard Business School Press, 1994), constituting a set of extremely important criteria that must be taken into account in the design and construction of the institution's strategy regarding the quality of staff and the possibilities increasing its level. Scientific management is revealed as a consistent remedy compared to empirical-chaotic leadership, because science has its say. The practical finality is imposed and due to these characteristics, the research projects that target the human resource of a preschool education institution (and not only) have at hand a series of landmarks to follow.

Figure 1 Scheme qualitative increase process factors

Discussion and conclusions

Increasing the quality of the entire educational process by raising the professional level involves a set of measures related to the natural desire to modernize, to continue the professional training of newly hired graduates through competition, because the accumulation of knowledge involves the accumulation of teaching experience and hence the increase professional competence (teaching).

Starting with the recruitment of staff with great potential, according to well-developed selective criteria (following the steps provided by current legislation - CVs, tests, references) (GA Cole, 2000) for vacant positions, it is an intrinsic responsibility of the manager to ensure a favorable climate for professional development, because, says Bernard Gazier (2003), the triad: general training - vocational training - accumulation of experience, ensures the preservation and development of the qualitative heritage of the institution.

Relatively recent studies by researchers Ch. Hoy, C. Bayne-Jardine and M. Wood (1999), Boxall P. & Purcell J, (2000) mention among the organizational indicators not only the efficiency of school management, but especially the professionalism of staff that determine the investment of trust of parents and students in the management team and in the team of teachers and non-teaching staff. Educational managers must know the methods, the specific techniques of management, in order to be able to solve the wide problems they face and which require in-depth knowledge in the field. Therefore, in order to increase the quality of teaching and non-teaching staff, the diagnostic procedure is required, so that all those involved know and recognize their level of competence, implicitly their position in the staff structure.

The analytical procedure maximizes its efficiency when it offers teachers the opportunity to understand, explain and interpret the importance of this benchmark, on the one hand in the particular situation of the effects on the group of children / class of students, and on the other hand when it is seen as level reached / or to be reached of the degree of preparation, cohesion, homogeneity, autonomy and efficiency in the educational act, etc. For these reasons, quality and the process of increasing quality itself represent and must represent ab initio a permanent constant of any educational institution, regardless of level.

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